

A SIMPLIFIED AND EFFICIENT METHOD OF SECRET MESSAGE CRYPTOGRAPHY**Prof. Ziad Alqadi**

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ABSTRACT

A simplified method of secret message cryptography will be introduced, the method will apply message encryption-decryption by using simple message blocking and message blocks rearrangement, and the method will eliminate the complex of logical and arithmetic operations used in other methods of data cryptography. The proposed method will use a complicated private key; this key will provide a good key space capable to resist hacking attacks. The private key components will be used to divide the message into blocks and to run a chaotic logistic map model to generate a chaotic key, which will be sorted to form the indices key required to rearrange the message blocks, the produced outputs of the method will be very sensitive to the selected values of the private key components.

The proposed method will be tested and implemented using various messages, the speed parameters will be calculated, and the speed results will be compared with other method speeds to show how the proposed method will decrease the encryption time and how it will speed up the process of message cryptography.

The quality and sensitivity of the proposed method will be examined to show that the proposed method will satisfy the requirements of good crypto method.

Keywords:

Cryptography, SM, block, reshaping, rearrangement, PK, CK, IK, CLMM, growth rate, population.

INTRODUCTION

Message is a set of characters organized in one row matrix [20-25] as shown in figure 1, this row matrix can be reshaped into 2D matrix by selecting the number of rows and the number of blocks by apply a simple reshaping operation, each column in the obtained 2D matrix will be treated as a block. The number of blocks will be selected by the user and it can vary from time to time (see figure 1). The block length will be a part of the used in the proposed method private key (PK) [11-19].

Message:**Message cryptography using blocking and blocks rearrangement****Various blocking**

My cbr	Methncaog	Mtnae	Mgyr gc bsre
epuklr	e oygncae	eogna	eepau kal rm
stsioa	scg idkrm	sg dr	s tpsbinorae
soincn	srrubn sre	srb r	scohilndcenn
agngkg	ayaslg an	aalba	argynog kagt
grg se	gppio lrnt	gpoln	
ea a m		ehcog	
pbure		ykce	
chlden		c ikm	
ryo at		runse	
		ysg n	
		pi rt	

Figure 1: Various ways of message blocking (example)

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The expansion of the use of the Internet and the frequent exchange of messages through it has led to an increase in the number of data hackers, which has turned the communication network into an unsafe network (see figure 2) through which the data hacker can steal the message and resend it in a way that serves his interests. In order to transform the communication network into a secure network (see figure 3), the message must be protected before it is sent and transformed into a message that cannot be read or benefited from [26-30].

Figure 2: Unsafe data communication network

Figure 3: Safe data communication network

The easiest way to secure the message is message cryptography. The crypto process as shown in figure 4 contains encryption function (EF) and decryption function (DF) [31-40].

Figure 4: Crypto process: a) encryption, b) decryption

A good crypto method must satisfy the following requirements:

- Quality

The encrypted message must be damaged and unreadable, the mean square error (MSE) measured between the source and the encrypted messages must be high, while the peak signal to noise ratio (PSNR) must be low.

The decrypted message must be the same as the source message, the MSE measured between the source and the decrypted message must be zero, while the PSNR must be infinite [41-47].

- Speed:

The method must minimize both the encryption and decryption times, thus it must maximize the throughput of message cryptography [48-55].

- Security:

The used PK must be complicated and it must provide good entropy (entropy >128 [83]) to make the key strong enough to resist hacking attacks, the produced outputs must be sensitive to the selected values of the PK components [56-63].

- Simplicity

The method must be simple by reducing the number of rounds and reducing the number of logical and arithmetic operation required to apply key generation and message encryption –decryption. The process of key generation must be simple and does not require long time for secret key generation [64-70].

- Flexibility:

The method must be efficiently used to treat short, medium and long messages.

The Private Key

The PK used in the proposed method contains three components: number of blocks (NB), growth rate (r) and initial population (x). NB will be used to reshape the message into 2D matrix with NB blocks (columns), while r and x with NB are used to run a chaotic logistic map model to generate a chaotic key (CK), the CK will be sorted to form the secret indices key (IK), which will be used to rearrange the message blocks [70-77].

Chaotic logistic map (CLM) is a nonlinear difference equation (see equation 1), which maps the maps the population value at any time step to its value at the next time step [77-84].

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$$X_{t+1} = rX_t(1-X_t) \quad (1)$$

Where:

X is the population

r is the growth rate

The calculated population values will be used as a data set to generate the secret indices key [71-80], the generated population will be sorted to get the indices key, this key will contain a set of unrepeated integer values, the first value will point to the minimum element in the data set, the second value will point to the second minimum and so on, the length of the key can be controlled by the user. The following example shows how to generate a 10 elements key with fractional values:

```
x=0.1;r=3.6;d=x;
length=12;
for i=1:length
x=r*x*(1-x);
k(i)=x;
end
[ff indices_key]=sort(k);
indices_key
indices_key =
```

1 11 7 5 9 3 2 12 8 4 6 10

The Generated population requires time generation [77-84], this time will rapidly increase when increasing the population length, table 1 shows how the key generation time will increase when increasing the length of population:

Table 1: key generation time

Population length	KGT(second)	Length	KGT(second)
100	0.000001	15000	0.167000
200	0.000001	20000	0.250000
400	0.003000	25000	0.379000
500	0.004000	30000	0.528000
1000	0.017000	40000	0.976000
2000	0.052000	50000	1.549000
2500	0.054000	100000	10.599000
4000	0.060000	200000	57.864000
5000	0.064000	400000	331.892000
10000	0.101000	1000000	2311.878000

From table 1 we can see that the selected length of the population will affect the method efficiency so we have to select a length less than 5000, thus the selected number of message blocks will be less than 5000, doing this we can minimize the KGT and thus minimize the encryption time (see figure 5) .

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Figure 5: KGT vs population length

The generated populations and thus the generated secret indices key will be very sensitive to the selected values of the PK components, any minor changes in these values will lead to change the contents of the IK as shown in figure 6:

Figure 6: Indices key sensitivity

The PK will have a length of 192 bits, this key will provide an entropy equal 192 (greater than 128 [83]), this entropy will make the key strong enough to resist hacking attacks, the key space provided by the key will be calculated using equation 1 [11 -18]:

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$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Key space} &= 2^{3 \times 64} \\
 &= 2^{192} \\
 &= \\
 &6.2771017353866807638357894232077 \times 10^{57} \\
 &\text{Combinations} \\
 \text{Entropy} &= 192 \qquad (1)
 \end{aligned}$$

Related works

Many methods for data cryptography were introduced by various authors, some of these methods were based on the standard methods DES and AES methods [1-10], other were chaotic and non chaotic methods [77-84].

The introduced methods shared the following features [1-10]:

- Data blocking:

The data to be encrypted is to divided into blocks, the block size is fixed and small.

- PK length and key space:

Mostly these methods used a long PK, and these keys provided a good key space with good entropy, making the key strong enough to resist hacking attacks.

- Rounds:

These methods were implemented using a fixed number of rounds; each round required a complex of logical operations to apply data encryption-decryption.

- Secret keys:

Each of the introduced methods required a set of secret key, the keys generation process required a complex of logical and arithmetic operations.

- Speed

These methods provided various speeds, from low speed to high (see table 2), the efficiency of these methods was decreased when increasing the data size.

- Simplicity

Mostly these methods were not simple, each method required a complex of logical and arithmetic operations to generate the required secret keys and to apply data blocks encryption and decryption.

The aim of this paper research is to introduce a new method for message cryptography, this method will use two rounds, the first round will be used to divide the message into blocks, while the second round will be used to rearrange the message blocks. The proposed method will simplify the process of cryptography and will speed up the process of message cryptography by decreasing the encryption-decryption time and increasing the throughput of message cryptography.

Table 2: Throughputs of the introduced methods

Introduced method	Average ETP (K bytes per second)	Introduced method	Average ETP (K bytes per second)
DES	86.7881	Chaotic [77]	141.2305
3DES	74.6363	Hyper chaotic [77]	636.3379
AES	90.3135	In [78]	888.8867
RC2	61.8961	In [79]	911.0352
RC6	155.5953	In [80]	638.4082
BF	561.3837	In [81]	360.4102
Non-chaotic [77]	170.3906	In [82]	384.9609

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The proposed method

The proposed method used a PK with three components, the first component is to be used to reshape the message into a selected number of columns, each column will be treated as a block, figure 7 shows an example of message blocking:

Message='Securing secret message using message blocking and rearrangement'

Figure 7: Message blocking (example)

The second and the third components in the PK are the growth rate (r) and the initial population (x), the values of these components with the value of the NB are used to run a chaotic logistic map model (CLMM) to generate a chaotic key (CK), the CK is to be sorted to form the indices key (IK) required to rearrange the message blocks, figure 8 illustrate an example of IK generation:

Figure 8: IK generation (example)

The contents of IK are used to rearrange the message blocks. In the encryption phase the blocks are to be arranged according to the contents (see figure 9 for illustration), while in the decryption phase the blocks are to be arranged by finding the position of the minimum value first, then the second minimum and so on as shown in figure 10.

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Figure 9: Proposed method encryption phase (example)

Figure 10: Proposed method decryption phase (example)

The encryption phase of the proposed method will be implemented applying the following steps:

Step 1: Inputs preparation:

- a) Get the message.
- b) Get the message length (L)
- c) Get the PK: r, x and NB.

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d) Calculate the block size.

Step 2: Dividing message into blocks:

Reshape the message to 2D matrix with NB columns.

Step 3: IK generation:

a) Use r, x and NB values to run a CLMM to generate CK.

b) Sort CK to get the IK.

Step 4: Message encryption:

a) Use IK to rearrange the message blocks.

b) Reshape the message to one row matrix to get the encrypted message.

The decryption phase will be implemented using the same steps as for encryption phase using the encrypted message as an input message and by applying the decryption as shown in figure 10.

For researchers and readers, who are interested in using this method, the following mat lab code can be useful:

%Encryption:

```
m='Message cryptography by blocking and rearrangement';
```

```
m=uint8(255*rand(1,10*1024));
```

```
L=length(m);
```

```
r=3.77;x=0.12;
```

```
R=320; C=fix(L/R);
```

```
m1=reshape(m,R,C);
```

```
for i=1:C
```

```
    x=x*r*(1-x);
```

```
    CK(i)=x;
```

```
end
```

```
[dd IK]=sort(CK);
```

```
for i=1:C
```

```
    d=IK(i);
```

```
    m2(:,i)=m1(:,d);
```

```
end
```

```
m3=reshape(m2,1,R*C);
```

```
m4=char(m3);
```

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%Decryption:

```

L=length(m4);
r=3.77;x=0.12;
R=320; C=fix(L/R);
m5=reshape(m4,R,C);
for i=1:C
    x=x+r*(1-x);
    CK(i)=x;
end
[dd IK]=sort(CK);
for i=1:C
    d=IK(i);
    m6(:,d)=m5(:,i);
end
m7=reshape(m6,1,R*C);
m8=char(m7);

```

Implementation and results discussion

The proposed method was implemented using mat lab 7 and using a computer with the following specifications:

Processor: Intel(R) Core(TM) i5-3210M CPU @ 2.50GHz 2.50 GHz
 Installed memory (RAM): 4.00 GB
 System type: 64-bit Operating System
 Pen and Touch: No Pen or Touch Input is available for this Display

Increasing the number of blocks will increase the size of generated IK, thus the CLMM running time will be increased, thus the efficiency of the method will negatively affected, so it is required to select the optimal value for NB. To show this fact a message of 10 K characters was selected and treated using the proposed method by varying the NB value, the encryption time (ET) in seconds was calculated and the encryption throughput (ETP) in K bytes per second also was calculated and table 3 shows the obtained results.

Table 3: Speed results when varying NB

NB	Block size (byte)	ET(second)	ETP(K bytes per second)
2048	5	0.1180	84.7458
1024	10	0.0480	208.3333
640	16	0.0260	384.6154
512	20	0.0210	476.1905
320	32	0.0150	666.6667
256	40	0.0140	714.2857
128	80	0.0090	1111.1
64	160	0.0060	1666.7
32	320	0.0050	2000.0
Optimal		Min ET	Max. ETP
16	640	0.0060	1666.7

From table 3 we can see that the optimal ET and the optimal ETP was achieved when using 32 blocks, it is also seen that choosing NB within the range 32 to 128 will optimize the speed of message cryptography (see figure 11).

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Figure 11: ET and ETP vs NB

A set of messages were selected and processed using the proposed method, block size was fixed to 256, the ET and the ETP were calculated and table 4 shows the obtained speed results:

Table 4: Speed results for various messages (block size=256 bytes)

Message length(K bytes)	NB	ET(second)	ETP(K bytes per second)
0.5	2	0.0050	100.0000
1	4	0.0050	200.0000
2	8	0.0040	500.0000
4	16	0.0050	800.0000
5	20	0.0060	833.3333
10	40	0.0050	2000.0
25	100	0.0080	3125.0
50	200	0.0120	4166.7
100	400	0.0260	3846.2
200	800	0.0830	2409.6
500	2000	0.4740	1054.9
Average			1730.5

From table 4 we can see the following facts:

- Increasing the message size will increase the ETP.

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- The maximum ETP will be achieved when reaching a 50 K bytes message length and this is the optimal ETP.
- Increasing the message size for messages with length greater than 50 K bytes will decrease the ETP (see figure 12)..
- Changing the block size and the message length will change the optimal ETP.
- The method provided a good average of ETP, which is equal 1730.5 K bytes per second..
- The method provided a speed up in message cryptography comparing with other existing methods (see table 5), the proposed method significantly increased the throughput of message cryptography.

Figure 12: ETP ns message length (block size =256 bytes)

Table 5: Proposed method speed up

Introduced method	Average ETP (K bytes per second)	Speed up of the proposed method	Introduced method	Average ETP (K bytes per second)	Speed up of the proposed method
DES	86.7881	19.9394	Chaotic [77]	141.2305	12.2530
3DES	74.6363	23.1858	Hyper chaotic [77]	636.3379	2.7195
AES	90.3135	19.1610	In [78]	888.8867	1.9468
RC2	61.8961	27.9581	In [79]	911.0352	1.8995
RC6	155.5953	11.1218	In [80]	638.4082	2.7106
BF	561.3837	3.0826	In [81]	360.4102	4.8015
Non-chaotic [77]	170.3906	10.1561	In [82]	384.9609	4.4953

The quality of the proposed method was tested, the decrypted messages were always identical to the source messages, while the encrypted messages were always damaged.

The previous selected messages were again processed by the proposed method, the obtained High values of MSE measured between the source and the encrypted messages and the low values of PSNR prove the fact that the proposed method satisfied the encryption quality requirements (see table 6):

Table 6: Encryption quality parameters(block size 256 bytes)

Message length(K bytes)	NB	MSE	PSNR
1	4	11305	17.4949
2	8	10902	17.8579

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4	16	10058	18.6637
5	20	10447	18.2843
10	40	10920	17.8415
25	100	10732	18.0150
50	200	10858	17.8986
100	400	10765	17.9851
200	800	10770	17.9803
500	2000	10841	17.9147

The sensitivity of the proposed method was tested, the message ' $10.6+7*5/2+12+23=63.1000$ ' was encrypted using the following PK, the encrypted message was decrypted by adding some changes to the PK, the obtained results shown in table 7 prove that the method is very sensitive to the selected values of the PK.

PK:

$r=3.77;x=0.12;$

NB=4;

Table 7: Proposed method sensitivity

Changes	Decrypted message
No changes	$10.6+7*5/2+12+23=63.1000$
NB=3	$5/10+16+3.1*0002.2+273=6$
$r=3.87$	$10.6+7*5/0002+12+23=63.1$
$x=0.22$	$2+26+7*5/3=63.10002+110.$

CONCLUSION

A simple and easy to implement method of message cryptography was proposed, the method used a simple message blocking and blocks rearrangements to replace the complex of logical and arithmetic operations used in other methods of data cryptography, the method used a simplified procedure to generate the secret indices by running a chaotic logistic map model. The proposed method provided a good security level, the entropy of the key is acceptable and it provide a strong enough key space capable to resist hacking attacks, the produced outputs were very sensitive to the selected values of the private key. The private key was used to apply message blocking and message blocks rearrangements based on the contents of the generated secret indices key. The message block size and the number of blocks were examined to provide an optimal efficiency.

The speed of the proposed method was examined by implementing the proposed method using various messages, and it was shown that the proposed method was efficient when processing short, medium and long messages. The proposed method provided a good average speed, and the speed results of the proposed method were compared with other existing methods speeds, and it was shown that the proposed method provided a significant speed up, it reduced the encryption time and increased the throughput of message cryptography. The quality and sensitivity of the proposed method were tested and it was shown that the proposed method satisfied the requirements of good crypto method.

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